

Nonlinear finite element analysis of composite bolted lap joints: experimental vs numerical tests

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Introduction and context

- Few composite parts on Falcon aircrafts
- Need to master composite bolted joint behavior to satisfy performance and safety requirements

Bearing = preferential failure mode for the design of bolted structures because of its progressive failure behavior

What are the physical phenomena leading to bearing failure of composite bolted joints ?

Nonlinear behavior of the composite material

Degrading mechanical properties

- In the different directions
- According to the load (tension, compression, etc.)

$$E_{11} = E_{11}^0 (1 - d_1)$$

$$E_{22} = E_{22}^0 (1 - d_2)(1 - d_2^b)$$

$$G_{12} = G_{12}^0 (1 - d_4)(1 - d_4^b)$$

Damage variables

- Correspond to the properties to degrade

$$d_1 = \phi_1 + \phi_2$$

$$d_2 = d_4 = \phi_4$$

$$d_2^b = d_4^b = \phi_4^b$$

Evolution laws and coupling

- Brittle failure or not
- Relation between physical phenomenon and properties to degrade ?

$$c_n = \max(\sqrt{f_n}, 1)$$

$$\phi_n = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{c_n m_n}{m_n}\right)$$

Failure criteria

- At ply scale level
- One failure criterion f_i for one failure mode based on measured failure stresses

$$f_1 = \left(\frac{\langle \sigma_{11} \rangle_+}{\sigma_{11}^{RT}}\right)^2 + \frac{\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2}{\sigma_{12}^{RC} \sigma_{13}^{RC}}$$

$$f_2 = \left(\frac{\langle -\sigma_{11} \rangle_+}{\sigma_{11}^{RC}}\right)^2$$

$$f_4 = \left(\frac{\langle \sigma_{22} \rangle_+}{\sigma_{22}^{RT}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\langle -\sigma_{22} \rangle_+}{\sigma_{22}^{RC}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{\sigma_{12}^{RC}}\right)^2$$

$$f_4^b = \left(\frac{\langle \sigma_{22} (1 - d_2) \rangle_+}{\sigma_{22}^{RT}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\langle -\sigma_{22} \rangle_+}{\sigma_{22}^{RC}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12} (1 - d_4)}{\sigma_{12}^{RC}/k}\right)^2$$

Double lap joint finite element model

Supported single lap joint finite element model

Conclusions and perspectives

- Double lap joint finite element model: good correlation between numerical and experimental tests thanks to the non linear composite behavior law
- Supported single lap joint finite element model: differences between numerical and experimental stiffness, bolt modelling has to be improved because beam theory hypothesis not verified $\frac{L}{\phi} \sim 1$
- Bolt tightening not taken into account because of shell finite element modelling
- Damage scenarios quite similar between double lap joint and supported single lap joints
- Interrupted tests on single lap joint specimens : validation of the damage scenarios using NDC
- Volume finite element modelling : bolt tightening taken into account, better modelling of the contact between the plates and the fastener, better modelling of the bolt, inter laminar behavior could be studied